

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Pharmacy

Title of the course: **Law & Ethics in Pharmacy Practice**

Level: **5th Class, 2nd Semester**

Credit hours: **Theory 2 hours.**

Reference Text:

1-1-Robert J. Cipolle, Linda M. Strand, Peter C. Morley. Pharmaceutical Care Practice: The Clinician's Guide. Latest edition.

2- Robert m. Veatch and Amy Haddad. Case Studies in Pharmacy Ethics. Latest edition.

3-pharmaceutical legislation in Iraq.

Objective:

In this course the students are expected to demonstrate a good awareness and understanding of pharmaceutical legislation, regulations, detailed laws that govern and affect the practice of pharmacy in Iraq. In addition, the course will provides an overview of ethical issues facing practicing pharmacists in order to enable the student to understand the basic concepts of ethics which formulate the relationship of pharmacist with the patient, colleges, and other health personnel.

No	Lecture title	hours
1	Introduction to Pharmacy Ethics (Theoretical considerations).	2
2	Code of Ethics for Pharmacists.	1
3	Common Ethical Considerations in Pharmaceutical Care Practice (Beneficence, Autonomy, Honesty, Informed Consent, Confidentiality, Fidelity).	3
4	Interprofessional Relations.	2
5	Making ethical decisions.	1
6	Ethical issues related to clinical pharmacy research.	1
7	Ethical problems in the pharmacist's clinical practice.	1
8	Preventing misuse of medicines.	1
9	Case studies in pharmacy ethics.	3
10	Important Pharmaceutical legislation in Iraq (ex. Those of syndicate of Iraqi pharmacists and Iraqi ministry of health)	7

11	Iraqi regulations regarding (Medical Prescription ,drug approval, herbal medicine approval, dietary supplement approval, (serums, vaccines and Biological Materials approval), Mental Substances, Cosmetics,)	8
----	---	---

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Pharmacy

Title of the course: **Pharmaceutical promotion and marketing**

Level: **5th Class, 2nd Semester**

Credit hours: **Theory 2 hours.**

ReferenceText:

- 1- Principles of marketing, Philip Kotler & Armstrong, latest available edition
- 2- Pharmaceutical marketing a practical guid, Dimitris Dogramatzis , latest available edition
- 3- Pharmaceutical marketing, Barent L. Rollin , latest available edition

Objective:

To provide comprehensive marketing overview in terms of marketing Principles and marketing concepts. Pharmaceutical marketing aspects and its applications in Iraqi market emphasizing Marketing strategy , marketing management , plan development. and consumer behavior aspects.

No	Lecture title	hours
1	Introduction to pharmaceutical marketing and pharmaceutical Industry environments	2
2	Marketing Research and situational Analysis	2
3	Segmentation ,Positioning and Targeting	3
4	Product life cycle	2
5	portfolio management	1
6	Competitive strategy	2
7	Marketing mix Concepts	5
8	Communication Strategy and Advertising (Communication strategy and process, Personal selling, Public relation and sales promotion, Advertising, Ethics in drug advertisement), Social media and web marketing	5
9	Promotional marketing Activities and practice	3
10	Forecasting, planning and evaluation	2

11	Consumer Buyer Behavior	1
12	case studies in marketing and promotion	2

College of Pharmacy

Department of **Pharmacognosy**

Title of the course: **Complimentary & Alternative Medicine**

Level: **5th Class, 2nd Semester**

Credit hours: **theory 2 hours.**

Reference:

- 1- Steven B. Kayne. Complementary therapies for pharmacists. Pharmaceutical Press. Latest edition.
- 2- V Schulz, R Hansel, V.E. Tyler. Rational phytotherapy, a physicians' guide to herbal medicine. Latest edition.
- 3- Steven B. Kayne. Complementary and Alternative Medicine. Pharmaceutical Press. Latest edition.
- 4- Kayne, Steven B. FASTtrack: Complementary and Alternative Medicine. Pharmaceutical Press. Latest edition.

Objective:

This course is intended to introduce pharmacy students to the concept of complementary medicine (CAM) and the different types of medicines commonly used by patients and complementary therapies recognized by international health authorities with emphasis on modern herbal remedies..

No	title	hours
1	Introduction to complementary and alternative medicine, systematic approach in herbal drug prescribing. Standardization of drugs , Bioassay fallow up.	2
2	Phytomedicines for respiratory system diseases (cold syndrome, cough, expectorants and sinusitis)	2
3	Phytomedicine for digestive system diseases (anorexia, dyspepsia, bloating, irritable bowel syndrome, acute diarrhoea, constipation and liver diseases)	2
4	Phytomedicine for cardiovascular diseases (heart failure, coronary insufficiency, hypotension & hypertension, atherosclerosis, chronic venous insufficiency)	2

5	Phytomedicine for CNS diseases (ginkgo, St. John's Wort, sleeping and restlessness remedies)	2
6	Phytomedicine for urinary tract diseases (inflammatory disease, benign prostate hyperplasia, bladder and kidney)	2
7	Phytomedicine for gynecological diseases (dysmenorrhoea, menopause)	2
8	Phytomedicine for skin and rheumatic diseases (inflammatory skin conditions, postoperative conditions, rheumatic and degenerative joint diseases)	2
9	Phytomedicine for enhancing immune system	2
10	Medicinal Teas (medicinal and non medicinal teas, actions, forms, soluble, guidelines for preparations and use in infants and children)	2
11	Drug-Herb Interactions	2
12	Other complementary and alternative medicine [Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) , Homeopathy, Aromatherapy, hydrotherapy, massage, chiropractic, osteopathy, magnetotherapy].	8

University of Baghdad

College of Pharmacy

Department of Clinical Pharmacy

Title of the course: Advanced Pharmacy Practice Experience **II**

Level: **6th Class, 2nd Semester**

Credit hours: **Laboratory 15**

Reference Text:

Manuals prepared by the Clinical Pharmacy Department.

Objective:

During the Advanced Pharmacy Practice Experience (clerkship), student will be involved in the provision of advanced clinical pharmacy services in various medical sub-specialty environments in specialized centers(units). The student will have experience of responsibilities (under direct supervision of preceptor). The following topics will be covered:

Paediatrics, Oncology/ haematology, Dermatology, Rheumatology.

No	Rotation name	weeks	Credit
1	Paediatrics	8	4
2	Oncology and haematology	8	4
3	Obstetrics, gynaecology and surgery	8	4
4	Rheumatology and dermatology	8	4
Total credits of 2 nd semester			15